

Maximizing the forecasting skill of an ensemble model

Marcus Herrmann^{1b} and Warner Marzocchi^{1b}

Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, dell'Ambiente e delle Risorse; Università degli studi di Napoli 'Federico II', L3 - 2.23, Edificio 10, Complesso Universitario di Monte Sant'Angelo, Via Cintia 21, 80126 Napoli, Italy. E-mail: marcus.herrmann@unina.it

Accepted 2023 January 17. Received 2023 January 12; in original form 2022 October 17

SUMMARY

An ensemble model integrates forecasts of different models (or different parametrizations of the same model) into one single ensemble forecast. This procedure has different names in the literature and is approached through different philosophies in theory and practice. Previous approaches often weighted forecasts equally or according to their individual skill. Here we present a more meaningful strategy by obtaining weights that maximize the skill of the ensemble. The procedure is based on a multivariate logistic regression and exposes some level of flexibility to emphasize different aspects of seismicity and address different end users. We apply the ensemble strategy to the operational earthquake forecasting system in Italy and demonstrate its superior skill over the best individual forecast model with statistical significance. In particular, we highlight that the skill improves when exploiting the flexibility of fitting the ensemble, for example using only recent and not the entire historical data.

Key words: Probabilistic forecasting; Statistical methods; Earthquake interaction, forecasting, and prediction; Statistical seismology.

1 INTRODUCTION

Forecasting future events in natural systems is often challenging. To capture the innate uncertainty, the forecast must be probabilistic (see Gneiting & Katzfuss 2014 for a full appraisal of the problem). The most advanced probabilistic forecasts combine a set of models that may be of different kind, ranging from entirely statistical (e.g. see Gerstenberger *et al.* 2020 for applications in seismic hazard assessment) to deterministic (e.g. Murphy & Palmer 1986; Folch *et al.* 2022). Combining the forecasts in a post process is meant to improve the forecasting skill over the individual forecasts (Krishnamurti *et al.* 2000, 2016; Palmer *et al.* 2004; Tebaldi & Knutti 2007; Marzocchi *et al.* 2012b). This combination, hereafter termed ‘ensemble model’, has different names in literature, such as multi-model ensemble (e.g. Palmer *et al.* 2004; Tebaldi & Knutti 2007; Knutti *et al.* 2017), superensemble (Bottazzi *et al.* 2021), multi-model superensemble (Krishnamurti *et al.* 2000, 2016), mixture model (Rhoades & Gerstenberger 2009; Rhoades 2013) or hybrid (Rhoades *et al.* 2014; Bird *et al.* 2015; Bayona *et al.* 2022), but it can be summarized as $f_E = g[\{f_i, \pi_i\}]$ ($i = 1, \dots, m$), in which $g[\cdot]$ is the ‘ensemble operator’, f_i are the candidate forecasts, π_i their corresponding weights and m the number of candidate forecast models. f_i is often expressed as the probability of exceeding a certain threshold x of hazard intensity X , that is a survival function $f(x) = \Pr(X > x)$.

To date, ensemble models usually collapse all forecasts f_i into one single forecast f_E . Although different probabilistic ensemble

strategies exist (Gneiting & Ranjan 2013), the most common approach involves the weighted average, that is linear combination, of $f_i(x)$:

$$f_E(x) \equiv \bar{f}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^m f_i(x) \pi_i. \quad (1)$$

Note that eq. (1) becomes the Bayesian model averaging (BMA) when treating π_i as the probability of $f_i(x)$ to be the true forecast, or, more pragmatically, the forecast that should be used (Scherbaum & Kahn 2011). The weights π_i should lead to a $f_E(x)$ that has a superior forecasting skill than any $f_i(x)$. For long-term forecasts, which are usually characterized by a few (if any) independent data for testing, weights are often assigned through qualitative experts’ elicitation schemes (e.g. Cooke 1991; see also Rhoades *et al.* 2016; Meletti *et al.* 2021; Gerstenberger *et al.* 2022). When sufficient independent data are available for testing (e.g. in short-term earthquake forecasting or weather forecasting), weights can be assigned more quantitatively. But no common strategy exists. Often, weights are set equal so that $f_E(x) \equiv \bar{f}(x)$ is the arithmetic average (Goreff 2000; Akinci *et al.* 2018) or weights are determined from the forecasting skill of the individual models (Marzocchi *et al.* 2012b; Knutti *et al.* 2017). Although the latter procedure sounds reasonable, Monteith *et al.* (2011) show that it does not lead to optimal results. To guarantee that $f_E(x)$ is the best combination of $f_i(x)$, weights should maximize the skill of the ensemble, and not depend on the skill of each individual model. Here we acknowledge this

idea and introduce a flexible weighting scheme that optimizes the skill of $f_E(x)$. To illustrate this advantageous procedure, we apply it to a practical case: the operational earthquake forecasting in Italy (Marzocchi *et al.* 2014).

In short-term earthquake forecasting, several ensemble models have been created using weighted averaging (eq. 1) of rate-based statistical models (Rhoades & Gerstenberger 2009; Marzocchi *et al.* 2012b; Rhoades 2013; Taroni *et al.* 2018; Llenos & Michael 2019). Although they did not always improve the forecasting skill considerably over the best-performing candidate, they never performed worse, which makes them ideal *a priori* choices (because one cannot know beforehand which candidate model will perform best). Some experiments have shown that when including models that are based on data other than earthquake rates, like strain or fault slip rates, a multiplicative procedure promised beneficial (e.g. Rhoades *et al.* 2014; Bird *et al.* 2015; Rhoades *et al.* 2017). Although prospective testing affirmed that such multiplicative ensembles can outperform their candidate models on long timescales (Strader *et al.* 2018), it also revealed that they were not more informative than the best forecast model on short timescales (Bayona *et al.* 2022). Shebalin *et al.* (2014) presented yet another type of multiplicative ensembling that updates a rate-based forecast with other numerical forecasts using differential probability gains. Despite the wide range of possible procedures to combine forecasts, we argue that only the weights of a weighted-average ensemble (eq. 1) give the opportunity to consider the dispersion of f_i instead of just collapsing them into one single distribution f_E . In other words, these weights optimize the forecasting skill of the first moment (weighted average) and can also be used to estimate the second moment (weighted variance), which reflects the dispersion of the forecasts and mimics the epistemic uncertainty (Marzocchi & Jordan 2014, 2017). Here we present a method to create such a weighted-average ensemble of multiple rate-based forecasts, demonstrate its flexibility with various modifications and report the forecasting skill in a pseudo-prospective fashion.

2 METHOD

For simplicity, we only consider a single hazard threshold x_0 and intend to create a point ensemble $\phi_E = f_E(x_0)$ instead of a full probabilistic ensemble $f_E(x)$. This simplification allows us to focus on the essential mathematical procedure without precluding generalizations to more complex cases. The goal of the procedure is to estimate the weights that maximize the skill of ϕ_E when enough observed data are available. An intuitive approach is to adopt a logistic regression, in which the dependent variable is binary and relates to the probability of at least one event (above hazard intensity x_0), and the independent variables stem from the individual forecasts $\phi_i = f_i(x_0)$. Since the resulting logistic model ϕ_E^{logistic} may underperform, as explained below, we use the logistic regression as a means to retrieve the weights π_i . With those we create a weighted average ϕ_E^{WA} (eq. 1) as the optimal combination of ϕ_i in terms of forecasting skill.

To model a binary observable, Y_j , in spatiotemporal bins, j , the logistic regression uses the logistic (sigmoid) function, here in particular its multivariate extension to incorporate more than one forecast:

$$\Pr(Y_j = y | \mathbf{u}_j) \equiv p(\mathbf{u}_j) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-g(\mathbf{u}_j)}} \quad (2)$$

with $g(\mathbf{u}_j) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 u_{1,j} + \dots + \beta_m u_{m,j}$,

in which $y = \{0, 1\}$ (i.e. either none, or at least one target event occurred in each spatiotemporal bin j , respectively), p is the output probability between 0 and 1, β_0 the intercept coefficient, $\beta_{1,\dots,m}$ the model coefficients and $u_{i,j} = \ln \phi_{i,j}$ the independent variables (i.e. the log-rates of the individual forecasts ϕ_i in each spatiotemporal bin j). The logistic regression has its name from being a linear combination on the logistic, or log-odds, scale $\ln \frac{p}{1-p} = g(\mathbf{u})$, that is the logistic function converts log-odds to probability.

The best fit to the observable, that is the β_0 and $\beta_{1,\dots,m}$ that optimize the skill of the ensemble, is obtained by maximizing the log-likelihood ℓ , the measure for the goodness of fit of the logistic regression:

$$\begin{aligned} \ell &= \sum_{i: Y_j=1} \ln(p_j) + \sum_{i: Y_j=0} \ln(1-p_j) \quad (3) \\ &= \sum_j [Y_j \ln(p_j) + (1-Y_j) \ln(1-p_j)], \end{aligned}$$

in which $p_j = p(\mathbf{u}_j)$. In other words, the logistic regression assesses how the forecasts describe the observed target bins ($Y_j = 1$) that occurred in the corresponding forecast windows. Typically, j will represent spatial cells of a region that are extended by their temporal state as new data becomes available. In real forecasting applications (like in our example described in the next chapter), forecast windows reach into the future. To obey the basic regression assumption that Y_j must be independent from $\phi_{i,j}$, the logistic model is fit pseudo-prospectively (like out-of-sample validation), that is only to data available at a certain time: past forecasts whose temporal forecast horizon have ended and the actual target events that occurred within them.

In Appendix A, we present a modification of the fitting procedure to reduce the computational demand in case of an abundance of data (> 1 million samples) and very rare target bins ($\ll 1$ per cent), such as in our case.

The fit logistic model $\phi_E^{\text{logistic}} = p(\mathbf{u}_j)$ could in principle be used to ensemble the forecasts, but it may not maximize the forecasting skill when models change their forecasts continuously (and significantly) for two reasons: it depends too strongly on β_0 , and the delayed estimation of β_0 caused by the forecast horizon amplifies this dependence. These circumstances are explained and illustrated in more detail in Appendix B, but summarized in the following. The first reason is due to the fit reflecting not only how the models performed relatively ($\beta_{1,\dots,m}$, i.e. how well *each* forecast described the observable), but also absolutely (β_0 ; ‘baseline log-odds’, i.e. by how much they deviated *collectively* in describing the observable). Especially β_0 largely depends on the models’ forecast rate in the target bins. If forecasts gave relatively high rates in those bins, that is performed well, β_0 will be positive, otherwise, β_0 will be negative. Using a positive β_0 for ensembling those same forecasts will increase the (well-performing) forecast rates and render them even better in forecasting the targets, but a negative β_0 will further decrease the (poorly performing) forecast rates and render them even worse in forecasting the targets. Hence, when ensembling the forecasts, β_0 exaggerates their absolute performance: it makes good forecasts better, and poor forecasts worse. The second reason is that $\beta_{0,\dots,m}$ is based on past data (i.e. previous forecasts versus observed events until current time) and will be used to ensemble *current* forecasts. If current forecasts differ from previous forecasts, which is the case for short-term forecast models especially during earthquake sequences, $\beta_{0,\dots,m}$ will be inappropriate due to still referring to the performance of previous forecasts. The effect may intensify for longer forecast horizons, which delay the adjustment of the fit,

that is increase the age of the last usable fit. (Increasing the update frequency would not improve this situation, because the forecast horizon needs to end before $\beta_{0,\dots,m}$ can be estimated). The strong and delayed dependence on β_0 makes ϕ_E^{logistic} an overall unreliable candidate for ϕ_E and motivates a reconsideration: while β_0 only captures the absolute performance of the forecasts, their optimal combination is only encoded in $\beta_{1,\dots,m}$, even though with a delay. To extract this optimal relative contribution, we map these coefficients to non-normalized weights as follows:

$$w_i = \begin{cases} e^{\beta_i} - e^\tau, & \text{for } \beta_i > \tau \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{with } i = 1, \dots, m; \quad (4)$$

we chose $\tau = 0$ because we assume that a forecast attributed with $\beta_i \leq 0$ by the logistic regression does not describe the observable well and would only degrade the skill of the ensemble; such a forecast should therefore receive zero weight. Choosing an exponential relationship for the mapping acknowledges that e^{β_i} is the odds ratio of the i -th model, that is the odds $e^{g(u)}$ multiply by this e^{β_i} for every one-unit increase in $u_i = \ln \phi_i$. Subtracting e^τ (in our case 1) from e^{β_i} ensures that w_i transitions smoothly to zero. Since the sum of w_i does not necessarily equal 1.0, the weights need to be normalized:

$$\pi_i = \frac{w_i}{\sum_j w_j}, \quad (5)$$

so that the weighted-average ensemble $\phi_E^{\text{WA}} = \bar{f}(x_0) = \bar{\phi}$ can be calculated with eq. (1).

Note that the second limitation mentioned above (delayed assessment of $\beta_{0,\dots,m}$) still affects ϕ_E^{WA} due to relying on $\beta_{1,\dots,m}$, which may be inappropriate due to the delay. But ϕ_E^{WA} completely avoids any dependence on β_0 .

3 APPLICATION TO OPERATIONAL EARTHQUAKE FORECASTING (OEF)

OEF gathers and disseminates authoritative information about the time-dependence of seismic hazards to help communities prepare for potentially destructive earthquakes (Jordan *et al.*, 2011). Seismologists are not able to predict large earthquakes with high probability in small spatiotemporal windows, but they are able to model the spatiotemporal clustering, which is the most striking deviation of the earthquake occurrence process from complete randomness. Such a clustering is particularly pronounced on timescales of days to weeks, but it may be still relevant for up to one decade or more (Parsons 2002; Faenza *et al.* 2008; Stein & Liu 2009).

The OEF system in Italy (OEF-Italy)

Here we consider OEF-Italy (Marzocchi *et al.* 2014), the first OEF system that adheres completely to the requirements reported by Jordan *et al.* (2011). OEF-Italy provides an ensemble forecast based on three different models ($m = 3$), namely ETAS.LM (Lombardi & Marzocchi 2010), ETES.FCM (Falcone *et al.* 2010), STEP.LG (Gerstenberger *et al.* 2005; Wössner *et al.* 2010). These three models were submitted to the CSEP (Collaboratory for the Study of Earthquake Predictability) forecast experiment in Italy (Marzocchi *et al.* 2010; Schorlemmer *et al.* 2010; Taroni *et al.* 2018). Since 2005 April, each model provides a weekly forecast of the earthquake rate for magnitude $M_L \geq 3.95$ in 8993 spatial cells on a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ grid that covers the Italian territory except Sardinia (see Fig. 1). This grid stems from the testing region of the corresponding CSEP experiment; the threshold of 3.95 is due to

using 0.1-binned magnitudes. The weekly forecasts are updated every day at midnight (00:00 UTC) and, from 2013 December onwards, after any event with $M_L \geq 3.45$; hence, forecast windows largely overlap. For the ensemble model $g[\{\phi_i, \pi_i\}]$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$) of those forecasts $\phi_i = f_i(3.95) \equiv \text{Pr}_i(M_L \geq 3.95)$, π_i were determined prospectively with a Score Model Averaging method (SMA; Marzocchi *et al.* 2012b), that is inversely proportional to the logarithmic Poisson score of each model. Therefore, the weights depend on the individual forecasting skill of each model; the highest weight is assigned to the best performing model. For a full description of the SMA ensemble, we refer to Marzocchi *et al.* (2014).

To date, OEF-Italy has been validated through prospective testing only during the 2012 Emilia earthquake sequence (Marzocchi *et al.* 2012a) and more recently for the 2016 central Italy sequence (Marzocchi *et al.* 2017). Here we compare the forecasting performance of the SMA ensemble with our proposed ensemble strategy based on the logistic regression.

Building an ensemble with the logistic regression

At each date (00:00 UTC) between 2005 April 16 and 2020 May 20, we fit the multivariate logistic model to past data: $\ln \phi_i$, the log forecast rates of the candidate models, and Y_j , the target earthquakes within the corresponding forecast periods binned to the testing region's grid (Fig. 2) encoded as '0' [no targets] or '1' [one or more targets]. To solve the optimization problem, we use the implementation of *scikit-learn* (Pedregosa *et al.* 2011) with the *liblinear* solver and a very low (10^{-8}) regularization strength to not impose any penalty on the amplitude of the coefficients. The 8993 spatial cells and 6227 overlapping forecast windows (5514 regular forecasts at 00:00 UTC + 713 irregular updates) produce ~ 56 million samples per forecast model, most of which are non-target bins (99.994 per cent). Although *liblinear* is the most computationally efficient solver for our case, we further reduce the computational demand by only using 10 per cent of the non-target bins, see Appendix A and an illustration in Fig. 2.

To obtain model weights π_i , we examine two temporal fitting schemes: using all data since the beginning (Fig. 3), or only data of the previous year (Fig. 4). The first scheme lets π_i converge over time, whereas the latter scheme lets π_i reflect only the recent performance of the candidate models. For both schemes, the most notable weight readjustment occurs during the L'Aquila sequence in 2009 April. Afterwards, the weights fluctuate slightly over time, for example during significant sequences like in Emilia in 2012 May, and in central Italy in 2016 August–November, but eventually converge because new data contributes increasingly less to the logistic regression. The latter scheme instead 'forgets' the models' performances after 1 yr, and the weights provide some insights into the best performing model in a certain period (Fig. 4). Accordingly, the ETAS.LM model appears to describe the observed target earthquakes best during the L'Aquila and central Italy sequences, but not during Emilia, which ETES.FCM appears to describe best. STEP.LG often plays a minor or no role.

Comparing forecast performances of ensembles and candidate models

To evaluate the forecasting skill quantitatively, we calculate the *information gain (IG) per event* (IGPE; Rhoades *et al.* 2011) relative

Figure 1. Map of the testing region (orange cells) and $M_L \geq 3.95$ earthquakes between 16 April 2005 and 26 May 2020 (filled circles); only earthquakes inside the testing region are considered as target events.

Figure 2. Example fit of the logistic function (thick grey curve) to one forecast model component (ETAS.LM) using 1 yr of data. The observable (here: target earthquakes with $M_L \geq 3.95$) is binned in spatiotemporal bins and becomes $y = 1$ if one or more target earthquakes occur within it. To reduce the computational demand of fitting, the non-target bins ($y = 0$) are undersampled to 10%, cause a bias in the estimated intercept β_0 that can be corrected (thick dashed curve, see Appendix A). For illustration purposes, the displayed data points are randomly jittered vertically (to not collapse them all on either 0 or 1) and shown with a transparency effect (to highlight denser parts). For reference, the thin dashed curve represents the 1:1 rate-to-probability mapping; the filled circle at rate $\lambda = 10^0 = 1$ would be intersected by the logistic function when $\beta_0 = 0$.

Figure 3. Applying the logistic regression over time using increasingly more data (first fitting scheme). Top: Logistic regression coefficients $\beta_{1,2,3}$ (coloured curves) for the three models and intercept β_0 (grey curve) after correcting for the bias due to undersampling non-target bins (see Fig. 2 and Appendix A); Middle: Regression coefficients mapped to non-normalized weights w_i ; Bottom: Normalized weights π_i ; the black bars at the bottom axis represent the number of target earthquakes per day.

to the SMA ensemble, which serves as reference model:

$$I_{A, \text{SMA}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (\ln(\lambda_{jk}^A) - \ln(\lambda_{jk}^{\text{SMA}})) - \frac{\hat{N}^A - \hat{N}^{\text{SMA}}}{N}; \quad (6)$$

model ‘A’ is synonymous with every model that we want to assess relatively, that is the logistic model $\phi_E^{\text{logistic}} = p(\mathbf{u})$, the weighted-average ensemble ϕ_E^{WA} based on the logistic coefficients, and each candidate model (ETAS.LM, ETES.FCM, and STEP.LG); λ_{jk} is the rate of a forecast ϕ in bin j that contains target earthquake k ; $\hat{N} = \sum_j \lambda_j$ is the total earthquake rate expected by a model; and N the number of target earthquakes. Using eq. (6), we build the cumulative IGPE (CumIGPE) over time, that is at each time step, incorporating all data since the beginning. The CumIGPE at the last time step is effectively the IGPE over the entire time period. To obtain a temporally consistent CumIGPE that is not biased by the irregular forecast updates, we only consider forecasts issued at 00:00 UTC. We use the t -test to obtain the 95 per cent confidence interval of the CumIGPE (Rhoades *et al.* 2011).

Figs 5 and 6 as well as Table 1 show the overall superior skill of the weighted-average ensemble ϕ_E^{WA} , independently of the fitting scheme. Especially for the second fitting scheme, ϕ_E^{WA} provides a higher CumIGPE than any other model—at almost all times (Fig. 6). Although ϕ_E^{WA} is significantly more informative than SMA,

its CumIGPE over ETAS.LM, the best-performing candidate model, is not significant (0.002 ± 0.019 and 0.016 ± 0.028 with 95 per cent confidence for the first and second fitting scheme, respectively). The logistic model ensemble ϕ_E^{logistic} performs worse than ϕ_E^{WA} and the SMA ensemble, but better than STEP.LG and ETES.FCM. Among all candidate models, ETAS.LM performs best especially due to its better performance during the 2009 L’Aquila and 2016 central Italy sequence (Figs 5 and 6), which the ensemble weights already reflected independently (Figs 3 and 4).

The skill ranking (by CumIGPE) of the existing forecasting models (1: ETAS.LM, 2: SMA 3: ETES.FCM, 4: STEP.LG) agrees with prospective evaluations of Taroni *et al.* (2018) in which those models ran in 1-d forecasting mode (they could not test ETES.FCM due to a software bug).

With the presence of overlapping forecast windows in OEF-Italy, we found that including all windows in the logistic regression (as done here) instead of skipping overlapping ones (not shown) stabilizes the coefficients and leads to ~ 0.015 higher CumIGPE. Apparently, even though overlapping windows only add redundant data, the additional sample points (especially of the target bins) matter in improving the skill.

For the second fitting scheme, we also considered different lengths of the temporal window and its influence on the CumIGPE of ϕ_E^{WA} : 2 yr (730 d) kept it comparable (0.074); 1.5 yr (550 d) slightly

Figure 4. Like Fig. 3, but applying the logistic regression only to data of the previous year (365 d; second fitting scheme).

Figure 5. Evolution of the cumulative information gain per event (CumIGPE) for each new ensemble (black curves, see legend) and candidate model (coloured curves) over the SMA ensemble (grey horizontal line) using the first fitting scheme (increasingly more data, see Fig. 3). The black bars at the bottom axis represent the number of target earthquakes per day.

Figure 6. Like Fig. 5, but using the second fitting scheme (only data of the last 365 d, see Fig. 4).

Table 1. CumIGPE of the two ensemble models (for three configurations) and the three candidate models over the SMA ensemble; these are the last values of each curve shown in Figs. 5, 6, and C2 respectively. The \pm -values represent the 95 per cent confidence based on the t -test (Rhoades *et al.* 2011).

Used events for fitting ensemble Fitting scheme of data	$M_L \geq 3.95$ (same as threshold magnitude of forecasts)		$M_L \geq 2.95$ (Appendix C)
	#1 (since start)	#2 (previous year)	#2 (previous year)
Logistic ensemble (weights), ϕ_E^{WA}	0.064 \pm 0.017	0.078 \pm 0.023	0.112 \pm 0.019
Logistic ensemble (model), ϕ_E^{logistic}	-0.064 \pm 0.030	-0.099 \pm 0.051	-0.057 \pm 0.041
ETAS_LM		0.061 \pm 0.027	
ETES_FCM		-0.191 \pm 0.035	
STEP_LG		-0.861 \pm 0.056	

increased it (0.097); and half a year (182 d) slightly decreased it (0.049).

Temporal evolution of the ensembles' and candidate models' forecasting skill

In the years before the L'Aquila sequence and independently of the fitting procedure, the ϕ_E^{WA} and SMA ensemble are relatively on par and perform better than most candidate models; ϕ_E^{logistic} performs mediocre. The L'Aquila sequence provided the largest lift in CumIGPE (i.e. positive IGPE) for the ETAS.LM model, which ϕ_E^{WA} and ϕ_E^{logistic} based on the second fitting scheme (Fig. 6) can exploit better than the SMA ensemble; ETES.FCM and STEP.LG degraded in CumIGPE. In the following years, in the absence of a major earthquake sequence, STEP.LG and ETES.FCM improve, while ETAS.LM degrades in CumIGPE. In this period, ϕ_E^{WA} and ϕ_E^{logistic} are barely decreasing in CumIGPE using the second fitting scheme (Fig. 6), because they are increasingly based on the two better-performing models (ETES.FCM and STEP.LG)—the ensembles based on the first fitting scheme (Fig. 5), which rely too strictly on ETAS.LM in this period, do not have this adaptivity to obtain such an advantage in CumIGPE. In Fig. 6, the CumIGPE lead of ϕ_E^{WA} over ETAS.LM is the largest just before the 2012 Emilia

sequence. With this sequence, both logistic ensembles dropped in CumIGPE, because the logistic regression had suggested too much weight for STEP.LG and ETES.FCM (see Fig. 4) due to their better performance during the previous year. Apparently, they were not skilled in describing the $M_L \geq 3.95$ aftershocks in the bins surrounding the main shock, which had happened in a region of small-to-moderate seismic hazard (Marzocchi *et al.* 2012a). With its overall higher rate forecast, ETAS.LM performed better in anticipating the aftershocks of the first large event (local magnitude $M_L 5.9$). Hence, the other two models were not the ideal models to include during the onset of this sequence—but the ensemble cannot incorporate this information timely due to the delay caused by the forecasting horizon (see Method and Appendix B). However, once ETES.FCM incorporated the $M_L 5.9$, it performed well in describing $M \geq 3.95$ aftershock seismicity (including another large $M_L 5.8$ and its aftershocks), leading to an ensemble (especially ϕ_E^{WA}) that did not drop further in CumIGPE relative to SMA. In the following years, the CumIGPE of ϕ_E^{WA} slightly degrades, albeit less than the best model ETAS.LM. During the 2016 central Italy sequence, ETAS.LM increases in CumIGPE, which ϕ_E^{WA} , however, cannot fully exploit timely because it was briefly weighting all three models to an about equal amount (Fig. 4). For this reason, the CumIGPE advantage of ϕ_E^{WA} is lower than before the sequence.

Using $M_L \geq 2.95$ target earthquakes for fitting the ensemble

The fitting procedure is flexible and allows using a lower magnitude threshold for optimizing the ensemble than the target magnitude threshold of the experiment ($M_L \geq 3.95$). A lower magnitude threshold ($M_L \geq 2.95$) introduces more target earthquakes and bins, making the logistic regression more sensitive to seismicity changes and the ensemble potentially more adaptive. Since changing the target prevalence affects the estimated β_0 , we demonstrate in Appendix C the necessary procedure to obtain an unbiased ϕ_E^{logistic} . Fig. C1 shows the logistic coefficients and the corresponding model weights. Fig. C2 and Table 1 report the resulting forecasting skill for both ensembles; overall, they are more skilled compared to using $M_L \geq 3.95$ events and the CumIGPE of ϕ_E^{WA} over ETAS.LM now becomes statistically significant (0.050 ± 0.019 with 95 per cent confidence), but ϕ_E^{logistic} still performs poorly.

We again varied the length of the temporal window for the second fitting scheme and found a different influence on the CumIGPE of ϕ_E^{WA} compared to using $M_L \geq 3.95$ targets: 2 and 1.5 yr slightly reduced it (0.104 and 0.103, respectively) and half a year increased it (0.121).

Using $M_L \geq 2.95$ target earthquakes and the second fitting scheme, we briefly report the influence of simple additional modifications related to the weights and the mathematical average in Appendix D.

Interpreting the performance evaluation

The temporal evolution of the candidate models' CumIGPE suggests when each model excels, even though it quantifies their relative performance over an ensemble that incorporates them. Accordingly, ETAS.LM is particularly performing well during sequences, and ETES.FCM and STEP.LG are better in the absence of those. ETES.FCM still performs relatively well during sequences (especially during 2012 Emilia), but not STEP.LG. The SMA ensemble creates a compromise forecast that performs well overall, but not well during sequences, which is the lead cause for falling behind the overall superiority of ETAS.LM in terms of CumIGPE. Apparently, SMA suffers from involving poorly performing models too much. Our weighting strategy, represented by ϕ_E^{WA} , combines the forecasts better, even exceeding ETAS.LM. ϕ_E^{logistic} , however, comes up short and suffers from the issues mentioned in Methods and elaborated in Appendix B (dependence of ϕ_E^{logistic} on a potentially highly inappropriate intercept β_0 when models change their forecasts significantly); it is the very reason that led us build ϕ_E^{WA} as an alternative.

The slightly better skill of ϕ_E^{WA} for the second fitting scheme indicates that not using all but only recent data is beneficial, because the ensemble becomes more adaptive and less constrained, that is better able to reflect sudden advances of one model during a sequence (like ETAS.LM)—another aspect that the SMA ensemble was missing. Using a lower magnitude threshold as a further fitting modification improves the skill over the long-term, but not consistently at all times (see Fig. C2, before the 2009 L'Aquila sequence). We suspect that incorporating more smaller events generally improves robustness, but that those complementary events do not always resemble the frequency and occurrence of larger ones, leading to occasional misrepresentations.

Several additional modifications presented in Appendix D further improved the skill, but only when applied separately, not simultaneously (see Appendix D for an interpretation).

4 DISCUSSION

We demonstrated that a weighting strategy that maximizes the skill of the ensemble (ϕ_E^{WA}) is superior to using weights based on the individual skill of the candidate models (SMA ensemble); ϕ_E^{WA} achieved what the SMA ensemble could not: overall providing significantly more informative forecasts than the best candidate model—even though the other candidates are overall less informative. In other words, our ensemble successfully exploits their individual strengths.

We originally anticipated that the logistic model itself represents the ensemble model, because it translates the individual forecasts into a probabilistic output. In fact, the logistic regression is typically used in probabilistic forecasting because the output is a probability rather than a discrete quantity, for instance in meteorology (Wilks 2009). However, we found that in our application, the intercept β_0 of the logistic regression strongly depends on, and amplifies, the absolute performance of the forecast models (see Appendix B). The underlying reason is likely the combined effect of short-term models changing their forecasts continuously (and occasionally significantly) and the intercept's sensitivity to very rare target events (~ 0.006 per cent in our case). Rare target events are known to bias the intercept (King & Zeng 2001). In weather forecasting, a low fraction of target events also has major implications for obtaining a reliable fit to the data (Hamill *et al.* 2008), limiting the calibration of forecast models. Despite the encountered limitation, we demonstrated that the logistic regression is not rendered unusable *per se*; we could use it to assess the relative performance of the models and infer their weights. Those weights formed a weighted-average forecast that is more skilled than the logistic model itself (see interpretation in previous section).

We demonstrated the flexibility of our ensemble strategy by tailoring data used in the fitting procedure in two different ways: limiting its historical scope and including more target earthquakes with a lower magnitude threshold than used for forecasting. Each modification improved the performance of the ensemble. This groundwork offers a starting point for building more sophisticated and flexible ensembles by varying the fitting scheme. Besides the additional modifications presented in Appendix D, many more degrees of freedom are imaginable to create a more skilled ensemble, such as using an exponentially decaying temporal window to pronounce the recent performance, or incorporating the spatial skill to account for the regionally varying seismicity and model performance.

However, additional modifications that further improved the skill (when applied individually, see Appendix D) were not beneficial when applied simultaneously. As mentioned in Appendix D, either this behaviour results from overfitting, or because applying those modifications universally to the whole time period cancels their individual benefits and poses an upper limit on the overall skill. Only in case of the latter, one could better harvest their potential by letting them vary temporally and adapt to the data (e.g. flexible length of the time window in the second fitting scheme, or spatiotemporally varying weights). Prospectively testing different ensemble configurations of ϕ_E^{WA} will be paramount to identify the most meaningful degrees of freedom.

Despite the various employed schemes and modifications presented here, the ensemble's skill advantage over the best candidate model, albeit being significant, remained relatively modest (IGPE of ~ 0.05). We suspect that the low diversity of the three candidate models considerably limited the ensemble potential; after all, they are all based on the same principles and assumptions (empirical/statistical modelling of earthquake clustering, determined background rate, etc.). Nonetheless, a sound ensemble as presented

here is expected to perform similar or better than the best candidate model or the arithmetic average of all candidates. Since the best candidate is not known at the beginning of a forecast experiment, this kind of ensemble is more reliable (and potentially the most skilled). Significant skill improvements will require diverse models (including physics-based approaches, for short-term earthquake forecasting like those proposed by Cattania *et al.* 2018; Mancini *et al.* 2019; Sharma *et al.* 2020; or Dahm & Hainzl 2022); diversity increases the predictive pool and enables various well-performing forecasting approaches to be exploited and ensembled.

Interestingly, short-term earthquake forecasting ensembles that incorporate also physical information are currently not, or barely, more informative in prospective tests (Steady *et al.* 2014; Bayona *et al.* 2022). It remains to be seen whether this barrier is due to the ensemble method, the limited skill of the candidate models or because models did not complement each other well. To explore the potential of ensembling short-term earthquake forecasts, we envision that our weighted-average ensemble ϕ_E^{WA} becomes part of upcoming CSEP experiments: Automatically building an ensemble of all participating models during an experiment eventually enables prospective evaluations of the ensemble approach and its various configurations. To allow others creating ensembles of existing forecasts for retrospective or pseudo-prospective evaluations, we will implement the procedure presented here in pyCSEP (Savran *et al.* 2022).

5 CONCLUSIONS

A weighting strategy that maximizes the skill of the ensemble deemed beneficial not only in theory, but also in practice using the logistic regression. First, it offered a superior skill over the best candidate model (and the preceding ensemble approach) with statistical significance; secondly, it is more flexible than an individual model. But to obtain a skilled ensemble in our application, we had to discard the fitted logistic model and instead map its coefficients to weights. Those weights then created a better-performing weighted-average ensemble of the candidate forecasts. Other forecasting domains may not need to take this detour. Yet, the obtained weights will be useful to quantify the epistemic uncertainty of the forecasts using the weighted variance (see Introduction).

We have highlighted the flexibility of the ensemble approach by varying the fitting scheme and exchanging the observable; each change also increased the ensemble's skill. Numerous other modifications beyond those proposed in the Discussion section may further increase the flexibility and skill of the ensemble. While improving the ensemble skill will require extracting more (diverse) information from the candidate forecasts, a more flexible ensemble approach will be practical for conforming with the multipurpose and authoritative character of OEF to address different end users (i.e. with a focus on recent seismicity, overall rate, spatial skill, etc.).

Since candidate models capture the current knowledge, they ultimately limit the skill of the ensemble. Here we used only statistical models, but the ensemble would undoubtedly benefit from a pool of diverse forecast models, which should include both statistical and physics-based approaches, and models that perform exceptionally well in particular situations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Max Werner and one anonymous reviewer for their comments, which helped improve the article. This study was supported

by the 'Real-time Earthquake Risk Reduction for a Resilient Europe' (RISE) project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No. 821115).

DATA AVAILABILITY

Our method is available as Python class at doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7477998](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7477998) (based on <https://www.gitlab.com/marcus.herrmann/ensembling-forecast-models-with-logistic-regression>) and envision an implementation in pyCSEP (Savran *et al.* 2022). We used several routines of pyCSEP, for example binning target earthquakes to the testing region's cells and calculating the information gain and its confidence interval. The forecast data of OEF-Italy can be requested from the corresponding author.

REFERENCES

- Akinci, A., Moschetti, M. P. & Taroni, M., 2018. Ensemble smoothed seismicity models for the new Italian probabilistic seismic hazard map, *Seismol. Res. Lett.*, **89**(4), 1277–1287.
- Bayona, J. A., Savran, W. H., Rhoades, D. A. & Werner, M. J., 2022. Prospective evaluation of multiplicative hybrid earthquake forecasting models in California, *Geophys. J. Int.*, **229**(3), 1736–1753.
- Bird, P., Jackson, D. D., Kagan, Y. Y., Kreemer, C. & Stein, R. S., 2015. GEAR1: a global earthquake activity rate model constructed from geodetic strain rates and smoothed seismicity, *Bull. seism. Soc. Am.*, **105**(5), 2538–2554.
- Bottazzi, M. *et al.*, 2021. The Italian open data meteorological portal: MIS-TRAL, *Meteorol. Appl.*, **28**(4), doi:
- Cattania, C. *et al.*, 2018. The forecasting skill of physics-based seismicity models during the 2010–2012 Canterbury, New Zealand, earthquake sequence, *Seismol. Res. Lett.*, **89**(4), 1238–1250.
- Cooke, R. M., 1991. *Experts in Uncertainty: Opinion and Subjective Probability in Science*. Oxford Univ. Press.
- Dahm, T. & Hainzl, S., 2022. A Coulomb Stress Response Model for Time-Dependent Earthquake Forecasts, *J. geophys. Res.*, **127**(9), doi:
- Faenza, L., Marzocchi, W., Serretti, P. & Boschi, E., 2008. On the spatio-temporal distribution of M 7.0+ worldwide seismicity with a non-parametric statistics, *Tectonophysics*, **449**(1–4), 97–104.
- Falcone, G., Console, R. & Murru, M., 2010. Short-term and long-term earthquake occurrence models for Italy: ETES, ERS and LTST, *Ann. Geophys.*, **53**(3), 41–50.
- Folch, A., Mingari, L. & Prata, A. T., 2022. Ensemble-based forecast of volcanic clouds using FALL3D-8.1, *Front. Earth Sci.*, **9**, 741841.
- Gerstenberger, M. C. *et al.*, 2020. Probabilistic seismic hazard analysis at regional and national scale: state of the art and future challenges, *Rev. Geophys.*, **58**, e2019RG000653.
- Gerstenberger, M. C. *et al.*, 2022. The seismicity rate model for the 2022 New Zealand National Seismic Hazard Model, GNS Science Report, GNS Science 2022/47
- Gerstenberger, M. C., Wiemer, S., Jones, L. & Reasenber, P. A., 2005. Real-time forecasts of tomorrow's earthquakes in California, *Nature*, **435**, 328–331.
- Gneiting, T. & Katzfuss, M., 2014. Probabilistic forecasting, *Annu. Rev. Stat. Appl.*, **1**(1), 125–151.
- Gneiting, T. & Ranjan, R., 2013. Combining predictive distributions, *Electron. J. Stat.*, **7**, 1747–1782.
- Goerss, J. S., 2000. Tropical cyclone track forecasts using an ensemble of dynamical models, *Mon. Weather Rev.*, **128**(4), 1187–1193.
- Hamill, T. M., Hagedorn, R. & Whitaker, J. S., 2008. Probabilistic forecast calibration using ECMWF and GFS ensemble reforecasts. Part II: precipitation, *Mon. Weather Rev.*, **136**(7), 2620–2632.
- Jordan, T.H. *et al.*, 2011. Operational Earthquake Forecasting. State of Knowledge and Guidelines for Utilization, *Annals of Geophysics*, **54**(4).
- King, G. & Zeng, L., 2001. Logistic regression in rare events data, *Political Anal.*, **9**(2), 137–163.

- Knutti, R., Sedláček, J., Sanderson, B. M., Lorenz, R., Fischer, E. M. & Eyring, V., 2017. A climate model projection weighting scheme accounting for performance and interdependence: model Projection Weighting Scheme, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, **44**(4), 1909–1918.
- Krishnamurti, T. N., Kishtawal, C. M., Zhang, Z., LaRow, T., Bachiocchi, D., Williford, E., Gadgil, S. & Surendran, S., 2000. Multimodel ensemble forecasts for weather and seasonal climate, *J. Clim.*, **13**, 4196–4216.
- Krishnamurti, T. N., Kumar, V., Simon, A., Bhardwaj, A., Ghosh, T. & Ross, R., 2016. A review of multimodel superensemble forecasting for weather, seasonal climate, and hurricanes, *Rev. Geophys.*, **54**(2), 336–377.
- Llenos, A. L. & Michael, A. J., 2019. Ensembles of ETAS Models Provide Optimal Operational Earthquake Forecasting During Swarms: insights from the 2015 San Ramon, California Swarm, *Bull. seism. Soc. Am.*, **109**(6), 2145–2158.
- Lombardi, A. M. & Marzocchi, W., 2010. The ETAS model for daily forecasting of Italian seismicity in the CSEP experiment, *Ann. Geophys.*, **53**(3), 155–164.
- Mancini, S., Segou, M., Werner, M. J. & Cattania, C., 2019. Improving Physics-Based Aftershock Forecasts During the 2016–2017 Central Italy Earthquake Cascade, *J. geophys. Res.*, **124**(8), 8626–8643.
- Marzocchi, W. & Jordan, T. H., 2014. Testing for ontological errors in probabilistic forecasting models of natural systems, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, **111**(33), 11973–11978.
- Marzocchi, W. & Jordan, T. H., 2017. A unified probabilistic framework for seismic hazard analysis, *Bull. seism. Soc. Am.*, **107**(6), 2738–2744.
- Marzocchi, W., Lombardi, A. M. & Casarotti, E., 2014. The establishment of an operational earthquake forecasting system in Italy, *Seismol. Res. Lett.*, **85**(5), 961–969.
- Marzocchi, W., Murru, M., Lombardi, A. M., Falcone, G. & Console, R., 2012a. Daily earthquake forecasts during the May–June 2012 Emilia earthquake sequence (northern Italy), *Ann. Geophys.*, **55**(4), 561–567.
- Marzocchi, W., Schorlemmer, D. & Wiemer, S., 2010. Preface to the special volume ‘An earthquake forecast experiment in Italy’, *Ann. Geophys.*, **53**(3), III–VIII.
- Marzocchi, W., Taroni, M. & Falcone, G., 2017. Earthquake forecasting during the complex Amatrice–Norcia seismic sequence, *Sci. Adv.*, **3**, e1701239.
- Marzocchi, W., Zechar, J. D. & Jordan, T. H., 2012b. Bayesian forecast evaluation and ensemble earthquake forecasting, *Bull. seism. Soc. Am.*, **102**, 2574–2584.
- Meletti, C. *et al.*, 2021. The new Italian seismic hazard model (MPS19), *Ann. Geophys.*, **64**(1), SE112.
- Monteith, K., Carroll, J. L., Seppi, K. & Martinez, T., 2011. Turning Bayesian model averaging into Bayesian model combination, in *The 2011 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, San Jose, California, 31 July–5 August 2011*, pp. 2657–2663, ed. Monteith, K., The 2011 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks
- Murphy, J. & Palmer, T. N., 1986. A real time extended-range forecast by an ensemble of numerical integrations, *Meteorol. Mag.*, **115**, 337–348.
- Palmer, T. N. *et al.*, 2004. Development of a European multi-model ensemble system for seasonal to inter-annual prediction (DEMETER), *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, **85**, 853–872.
- Parsons, T., 2002. Global Omori law decay of triggered earthquakes: large aftershocks outside the classical aftershock zone, *J. geophys. Res.*, **107**(B9), 2199.
- Pedregosa, F. *et al.*, 2011. Scikit-learn: machine learning in Python, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, **12**, 2825–2830. Available at: <https://scikit-learn.org>
- Rhoades, D. A., 2013. Mixture models for improved earthquake forecasting with short-to-medium time horizons, *Bull. seism. Soc. Am.*, **103**(4), 2203–2215.
- Rhoades, D. A., Christophersen, A. & Gerstenberger, M. C., 2017. Multiplicative earthquake likelihood models incorporating strain rates, *Geophys. J. Int.*, **208**(3), 1764–1774.
- Rhoades, D. A. & Gerstenberger, M. C., 2009. Mixture models for improved short-term earthquake forecasting, *Bull. seism. Soc. Am.*, **99**(2A), 636–646.
- Rhoades, D. A., Gerstenberger, M. C., Christophersen, A., Zechar, J. D., Schorlemmer, D., Werner, M. J. & Jordan, T. H., 2014. Regional earthquake likelihood models II: information gains of multiplicative hybrids, *Bull. seism. Soc. Am.*, **104**(6), 3072–3083.
- Rhoades, D. A., Schorlemmer, D., Gerstenberger, M. C., Christophersen, A., Zechar, J. D. & Imoto, M., 2011. Efficient testing of earthquake forecasting models, *Acta Geophys.*, **59**(4), 728–747.
- Rhoades, D. A., Liukis, M., Christophersen, A. & Gerstenberger, M. C., 2016. Retrospective tests of hybrid operational earthquake forecasting models for Canterbury, *Geophys. J. Int.*, **204**(1), 440–456.
- Savran, W. H. *et al.*, 2022. pyCSEP: a python toolkit for earthquake forecast developers, *Seismol. Res. Lett.*, **93**(5), 2858–2870.
- Scherbaum, F. & Kuhen, N. M., 2011. Logic tree branch weights and probabilities: summing up to one is not enough, *Earthq. Spectra*, **27**(4), 1237–1251.
- Schorlemmer, D., Christophersen, A., Rovida, A., Mele, F., Stucchi, M. & Marzocchi, W., 2010. Setting up an earthquake forecast experiment in Italy, *Ann. Geophys.*, **53**, 1–9.
- Sharma, S., Hainzl, S., Zöeller, G. & Holschneider, M., 2020. Is Coulomb stress the best choice for aftershock forecasting?, *J. geophys. Res.*, **125**(9).e2020JB019553
- Shebalin, P. N., Narteau, C., Zechar, J. D. & Holschneider, M., 2014. Combining earthquake forecasts using differential probability gains, *Earth Planets Space*, **66**(1), 37.
- Stacy, S., Gerstenberger, M. C., Williams, C., Rhoades, D. & Christophersen, A., 2014. A new hybrid Coulomb statistical model for forecasting aftershock rates, *Geophys. J. Int.*, **196**(2), 918–923.
- Stein, S. & Liu, M., 2009. Long aftershock sequences within continents and implications for earthquake hazard assessment, *Nature*, **462**(7269), 87–89.
- Strader, A., Werner, M. J., Bayona, J. A., Maechling, P. J., Silva, F., Liukis, M. & Schorlemmer, D., 2018. Prospective Evaluation of Global Earthquake Forecast Models: 2 Yrs of Observations Provide Preliminary Support for Merging Smoothed Seismicity with Geodetic Strain Rates, *Seismol. Res. Lett.*, **89**(4), 1262–1271.
- Taroni, M. *et al.*, 2018. Prospective CSEP evaluation of 1-day, 3-month, and 5-yr earthquake forecasts for Italy, *Seismol. Res. Lett.*, **89**(4), 1251–1261.
- Tebaldi, C. & Knutti, R., 2007. The use of the multi-model ensemble in probabilistic climate projections, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. A.*, **365**(1857), 2053–2075.
- Wilks, D. S., 2009. Extending logistic regression to provide full-probability-distribution MOS forecasts, *Meteorol. Appl.*, **16**(3), 361–368.
- Woessner, J., Christophersen, A., Zechar, J. D. & Monelli, D., 2010. Building self-consistent, short-term earthquake probability (STEP) models: improved strategies and calibration procedures, *Ann. Geophys.*, **53**(3), 141–154.

APPENDIX A. USING FEWER DATA OF NON-TARGET BINS

To increase the computational efficiency of fitting the logistic model to OEF-Italy (totaling ~ 56 million samples per forecast model, of which 99.994 per cent are non-target bins), we only use $r_0 = 10$ per cent of the non-target bins (while keeping all target bins). As long as r_0 is not too small, the increased uncertainty in $\beta_{1,\dots,m}$ due to fewer data is negligible, and therefore its impact on ϕ_E^{WA} . However, this modification (‘undersampling’, which is related to case-control sampling) changes the prevalence of target bins and causes a bias in the estimated β_0 (King & Zeng 2001), which would considerably degrade the forecasting skill of ϕ_E^{logistic} . To obtain a bias-corrected β_0 , King & Zeng (2001) provide a correction based on the prevalence in the original data and the undersampled data. If the prevalence is still very small in the undersampled data, such as in our case, the bias can be approximated with $\beta_0^{\text{bias}} = -\ln r_0 = -\ln 0.1$ (proof not shown here), as illustrated in Fig. 2.

APPENDIX B. ILLUSTRATING THE POOR SKILL OF THE LOGISTIC ENSEMBLE MODEL, ϕ_E^{logistic}

In the following we explain and illustrate why the logistic model itself, as fit with the logistic regression, does not provide a reliable ensemble when models change their forecasts continuously (and significantly) for two reasons:

- (i) it exaggerates their relative performance, making good forecasts better, and poor forecasts worse;
- (ii) the delayed estimation of the fit caused by the forecast horizon amplifies this exaggeration.

We demonstrate these limitations by illustrating and interpreting obtained fits for two extreme examples: during the 2006 L'Aquila sequence (Table B1), in which the ETAS.LM performed very well, and the 2012 Emilia sequence (Table B2), in which all forecasts performed poorly. The first figure in Tables B1 and B2 gives a temporal overview of the target earthquakes and the times of the issued forecasts. For the sake of illustration, we do not show fits for every update interval (ticks on time axis), but only in steps of the forecasting horizon (7 d, vertical lines), resulting in four points in time with corresponding fits:

- (i) before a foreshock;
- (ii) including a foreshock, before the main shock;
- (iii) including the foreshock, main shock and aftershocks;
- (iv) including even more aftershocks.

Those fits resemble the second fitting scheme (using data of the last 365 d). For simplicity, we fit only a single forecast model—the one that received the highest weight in the multivariate fit: ETAS.LM performed best during the L'Aquila sequence, and ETAS.FCM during the Emilia sequence. Each shown fit in the individual rows of Tables B1 and B2 is similar to Fig. 2; fit logistic curves with $\beta_0 > 0$ are above the filled circle at $\lambda = 10^0 = 1$, and those with $\beta_0 < 0$ below.

Each row in the tables refer to a certain point in time ('now'). The first line in the comment field of each row summarizes the temporal range of the used data; note that the fit always refers to how the *previous* forecasts performed, not the current ones issued 'now'.

Given the observation in Table B1, it seems that ϕ_E^{logistic} does exactly what it should: during a sequence, it gradually outputs higher forecast rates than ETAS.LM and therefore performs better than ETAS.LM in terms of CumIGPE (see Fig. 6). However, this improvement is only coincidentally, as demonstrated with an application to the 2012 Emilia sequence in Table B2.

Even though the sequences in Tables B1 and B2 are comparable, the logistic fit behaves completely different. For the Emilia sequence, β_0 only became positive once the fit was based on forecasts that were 'aware' of the sequence; before, the logistic model translated forecast rates to much lower probabilities. Consequently, the CumIGPE of ϕ_E^{logistic} degraded during the sequence, even though it increased for ETAS.FCM (see Fig. 6).

The biggest difference between both cases is how the forecasts performed before incorporating the main shock and its aftershocks: they performed relatively well in the L'Aquila case ($\beta_0 > 0$), but not for the Emilia case ($\beta_0 < 0$). Therefore, β_0 reflects how much the models' forecast rates in target bins separate from forecast rates in non-target bins. In other words: if a target earthquake or sequence occurs in regions with low forecast rates (low expected seismicity), ϕ_E^{logistic} will perform poorly; if it occurs in regions with high

expected seismicity, ϕ_E^{logistic} may perform even better than the candidate forecasts. Applying it to the forecasts for which it was assessed will only amplify the absolute performance; it may or may not lead to an improved forecast. The amplification intensifies when large events occur, because they trigger several more target earthquakes in the surrounding bins, which is either expected or unexpected.

In addition, the fit is delayed, because it can be estimated only after the forecast horizon end. This delay is a *contributing* reason for the poor forecasting skill of ϕ_E^{logistic} , but not the main one, which can be demonstrated by simulating a zero delay. To obtain zero delay, we do not wait for the last forecast horizon to end, but leak in future target earthquakes, which we normally would not have (like a retrospective validation). The fit is made for currently issued forecasts vs. target earthquakes that will happen in the future forecast window (acausal); this fit is directly used to ensemble those forecasts (i.e. the ensemble is not independent of the observation). Effectively, this fit is the same that will be obtained after this forecast horizon ended—but to obtain zero delay it is already used in advance. The forecasting skill of this acausal ϕ_E^{logistic} is shown in Fig. B1. Overall, it performs slightly worse than the corresponding acausal ϕ_E^{WA} , indicating that ϕ_E^{logistic} offers no advantage over mapping coefficients to weights as done in this study, and proving β_0 as the culprit. Note that the higher CumIGPE of ϕ_E^{logistic} over ϕ_E^{WA} after the L'Aquila sequence is due to the effect described in Table B1.

This zero-delay procedure was repeated using only ETAS.LM forecasts (see Fig. B1) and a univariate logistic regression. Overall, this acausal $p(\lambda)_{\text{ETAS.LM}}^{\text{logistic}}$ performs similar to ETAS.LM itself. So even with zero delay, the logistic model cannot improve the forecast—due to the strong dependence on β_0 .

APPENDIX C. USING DIFFERENT EVENTS FOR FITTING THE ENSEMBLE

Changing the magnitude threshold changes the target prevalence and therefore adds a further bias on in the estimated $\tilde{\beta}_0$, which would degrade the forecasting skill of ϕ_E^{logistic} . Similar to the bias due to undersampling non-target bins (Appendix A), the bias due to different target bins depends on their relative change caused by a different magnitude threshold. Although non-target bins change as well, their relative change can be neglected since they are much larger in absolute number. The bias can be corrected by subtracting $\beta_0^{\text{bias}} = \ln r_1$, with r_1 being the ratio between the number of target bins, N_{bins} , for the new magnitude threshold, m_t , and the original one, $M_L \geq 3.95$: $r_1 = \frac{N_{\text{bins}}^{m_t}}{N_{\text{bins}}^{M_L \geq 3.95}}$.

We decreased the magnitude threshold to $M_L \geq 2.95$ and reapplied the second fitting scheme (using only data of the previous 365 d). Since we also undersampled the non-target bins (Appendix A), both biases need to be subtracted from $\tilde{\beta}_0$. The logistic regression coefficients and corresponding model weights are shown in Fig. C1; the forecasting skill of the obtained ensembles is shown in Fig. C2.

APPENDIX D. ADDITIONAL MODIFICATIONS

Using $M_L \geq 2.95$ target earthquakes and the second fitting scheme, we briefly report and discuss the influence of simple additional modifications related to the weights and the mathematical average. For instance, the weighted (arithmetic) average employed in eq. (1) is a special case of the weighted generalized

Table B1. Illustrating and interpreting the logistic fits obtained during the 2006 L'Aquila sequence.

(or power) mean $\left(\sum_{i=1}^m f_i(x)^p \pi_i\right)^{1/p}$ with $p = 1$. Using an exponent of $p = 0$, that is the limit of $p \rightarrow 0$ (weighted geometric mean, CumIGPE 0.064), $p = -1$ (weighted harmonic mean, CumIGP -0.072), or $p = 3$ (cubic mean, CumIGPE 0.108) decreased the skill over $p = 1$, whereas $p = 2$ (weighted quadratic mean), or $p = [1.5, 2.0]$ in general, led to a slightly higher CumIGPE (0.115). $p = 0$ effectively creates a multiplicative ensemble $f_E(x) \equiv \left(\prod_{i=1}^m f_i(x) \pi_i\right)^{1/m} = e^{\sum_{i=1}^m \ln f_i(x) \pi_i}$, but its lower CumIGPE (0.064) indicates that the logistic regression optimizes model contributions more in an additive sense. Note that $p \neq 1$ is incompatible with the weighted variance to capture the dispersion of

the candidate forecast f_i and quantify the epistemic uncertainty (see Introduction).

Another weight-related modification concerns τ in eq. (4): setting $\tau = -0.2$ decreases CumIGPE to 0.108, whereas $\tau = 0.2$ improves it to 0.125; however, for the original $M_L \geq 3.95$ targets, CumIGPE behaves in the opposite way (0.089 and 0.067, respectively).

Interestingly, taken all choices together that individually led to a higher CumIGPE for $M_L \geq 2.95$ (i.e. second fitting scheme with a temporal window of half a year; $p = 2$; and $\tau = 0.2$) does not further improve the skill (0.119 ± 0.020). This limit may be caused by each modification impacting the IGPE positively or negatively (i.e. the temporal evolution of CumIGPE) depending on the situation and the other parameters. If several modifications create complex inter-

Table B2. Illustrating and interpreting the logistic fits obtained during the 2006 L'Aquila sequence (notable differences to Table B1 highlighted in bold)

actions that compensate skill improvements, the final CumIGPE does not grasp their potential relevance. That those interactions are complex is confirmed by changing the window length of the second fitting scheme, which has opposite influence on the skill for

$M_L \geq 3.95$ and $M_L \geq 2.95$ target earthquakes. Another possibility is that those skill improvements are caused by overfitting (variance due to sensitivity to random, i.e. uninformative, fluctuations in the used data set).

Figure B1. Like Fig. 6, but using an acausal logistic regression, which is based on target earthquakes that will occur in the future, i.e. zero delay. Both ensembles are therefore acausal. For comparison, an acausal logistic regression was also applied solely to the ETAS_LM forecasts (red dashed curve).

Figure C1. Like Fig. 4 (using only data of the previous 365 d), but with the logistic regression based on targets events obtained for a lower magnitude threshold ($M_L \geq 2.95$).

Figure C2. Like Fig. 6 (using only data of the previous 365 d), but using a lower magnitude threshold ($M_L \geq 2.95$).